

DIALECT LEXICOGRAPHY¹

Chitsuko FUKUSHIMA¹, Maria-Pilar PEREA² & Eveline WANDL-VOGT³

¹ University of Niigata Prefecture

chitsuko@unii.ac.jp

² Universitat de Barcelona

mpilar.perea@ub.edu

³ Institut für Corpuslinguistik und Texttechnologie (ICLTT)

eveline.wandl-vogt@oeaw.ac.at

Abstract

We briefly introduce the papers in this special issue of *Dialectologia* devoted to dialect lexicography and to the results obtained from different on-going projects. The papers focus on several aspects of the presence of dialects in dictionaries already published, some of them historical, as well as contemporary ones, which help to register both linguistic varieties that are at danger of disappearing as the results of new contacts and language exchanges.

LEXICOGRAFÍA DIALECTAL

Resumen

He aquí una breve presentación de los artículos publicados en este número extraordinario dedicado a la lexicografía dialectal y a los resultados obtenidos de los diferentes proyectos en curso. Los trabajos se centran en diversos aspectos de la presencia de los dialectos en diccionarios ya publicados, algunos de ellos históricos, así como en los contemporáneos, que contribuyen a registrar tanto las variedades lingüísticas que están en peligro de desaparecer como el producto de los nuevos contactos e intercambios lingüísticos.

¹ This special issue has been supported by the Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (research project FFI2010-18940 (subprograma FILO)).

This fourth special issue of *Dialectologia* aims to show the multiple relationships that can be established between two linguistic disciplines: dialectology and lexicography both from a diachronic and a synchronic perspective. The origin of this publication was the workshop held in Vienna in July 2012 under the 7th Congress of the International Society of Dialectology and Geolinguistics. There, participants showed their interest in the connection between dictionaries and geographic linguistic varieties, and this issue intends to echo the projects and works that fit under the heading of “dialect lexicography”.

The papers

The papers published in this issue are a heterogeneous sample of the on-going projects on dialectal lexicography and their results.

Xosé Afonso Álvarez Pérez and Xulio Sousa’s paper “The *tesouro do léxico patrimonial galego e portugués*. A Galician and Portuguese word bank” describes a dialectal lexical portal on the internet that brings together unpublished lexicographical material from these three countries in order to develop studies which particularly focus on names, historical linguistics, etymology and morphology.

From a historical point of view, the contribution of Christina Bassea-Bezantakou and Io Manolessou “The historical dictionary of modern Greek: dialectological issues” aims to review the objectives, history, and recent innovations of this dictionary that comprises not only standard modern Greek but also its different dialects.

Germà Colón’s paper, “An approach to Catalan dialect lexicography” examines and chronicles the presence of dialects throughout the history of Catalan lexicography, paying special attention to the treatment that dialect forms have received in dictionaries, especially from the 15th century onwards.

Using statistical calculations, the paper by Hiroto Ueda “A note on quantitative methods of taxonomy with large data. Coefficient of association applied to the variants of the *Diccionario de americanismos*” describes and examines different association coefficients. The author applies the most convenient index, called “greater association

coefficient”, to treat American Spanish materials obtained from the *Diccionario de Americanismos*.

Japanese historical dialect lexicography is reviewed by Chitsuko Fukushima, who particularly emphasises present-day dialect dictionaries, studies them from five different perspectives, and gives importance to the present-day technologies that help to raise awareness of them.

Fukushima, together with Yumi Nakajima and Motoei Sawaki, has worked in a project for a long time the main result of which has been the edition of the *Two Thousand Sentences of Tokunoshima Dialect*. This work, which reflects the local life of this Japanese archipelago, contributes at the same time to describing and preserving an endangered dialect. Nakajima’s paper “Making a dialect dictionary from a sentence-based corpus” describes the development of the project and its results, and Sawaki’s paper “Dialect dictionary in a DVD” examines the techniques used to process and publish these lexicographic materials.

While Japanese dialect lexicography has been well represented, Fumio Inoue’s contribution “Dialect lexicography and the standard language — words for *snow* and suburban Tokyo dialect” deals with contemporary Japanese dialects and the different sorts of relationships that can be established between them and the standard.

Continuing the researches in Asia, Takashi Matsue’s paper “Old Chinese dialects according to Fangyan” examines what has been considered the oldest dialect dictionary in China, created in the late second or early first century B.C. This work is unique because not only shows the areas of distribution of the words included but also gives account of contemporaneous colloquial expressions as well as minority languages.

Returning to Europe, “Dialect lexicography in Latvia. Accomplishments and opportunities” by Liene Markus-Narvila examines the present situation in Latvian dialect lexicography through the study of different published dictionaries, and explores its future based on the creation on new scientific dictionaries of regional subdialects and subject-specific electronic dictionaries of subdialects.

Mateusz Maselko’s paper “*Hunsrik Xraywe*. A new way in lexicography of the German language island in southern Brazil” explains the results of the *Equipe Hunsrik*

project, which works on the standardization, expansion, and dissemination of the German dialect variety spoken in Rio Grande do Sul (South Brazil). The main aim of the project is the insertion of Riograndese Hunsrik as official community language of this Brazilian state.

Finally, Eveline Wandler-Vogt's paper "Come collegare un dizionario tradizionale dialettale con Multimedia. L'esempio Banca dati dei dialetti Bavaresi in Austria (Datenbank der bairischen Mundarten in Österreich – DBÖ)" discusses the role of visualisations using the Dictionary of Bavarian Dialects in Austria (*WBÖ*) and the electronically mapped Database of Bavarian Dialects in Austria (*dbo@ema*) as examples.

Acknowledgments

We are grateful to each of the authors for their work, as well as the Vice-Rectorate of Communication and Projection at the University of Barcelona for the financial support that has made this special issue possible.